

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING GRAMMAR ON THE BASIS OF COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

This article is about effective methods which are implemented language teaching coincides with communicative one. These methods are utilized in the process of grammar teaching, as well as some instructions are presented to enhance this domain.

KEYWORDS

grammar

translation method

teaching

communicative language

grammatical structures

1. Introduction

Grammar itself was an academic exercise rather than one which would actually help learners to use language, and an overt focus on grammar was to learn about the target language rather than to learn it. But at the height of the communicative approach to language learning in the 1980s and early 1990s it became fashionable in some quarters to deride so-called old-fashioned methods and, in particular, something broadly labeled "Grammar Translation". As with many other methods and approaches, Grammar Translation tended to be referred to in the past tense as if it no longer existed and had died out to be replaced world-wide by the fun and motivation of the communicative classroom. In examination of the principal features of Grammar Translation, however, we will see that not only has it not disappeared but that many of its characteristics have been central to language teaching throughout the ages and are still valid today.

2. Methods

The Grammar Translation method embraces a

wide range of approaches but, broadly speaking, foreign language study is seen as a mental discipline, the goal of which may be to read literature in its original form or simply to be a form of intellectual development. The basic approach is to analyze and study the grammatical rules of the language, usually in an order roughly matching the traditional order of the grammar of Latin, and then to practice manipulating grammatical structures through the means of translation both into and from the mother tongue. The method is very much based on the written word and texts are widely in evidence. A typical approach would be to present the rules of a particular item of grammar, illustrate its use by including the item several times in a text, and practice using the item through writing sentences and translating it into the mother tongue. The text is often accompanied by a vocabulary list consisting of new lexical items used in the text together with the mother tongue translation. Accurate use of language items is central to this approach.

Generally speaking, the medium of instruction is the mother tongue, which is used to explain conceptual problems and to discuss the use of a particular grammatical structure. It all

sounds rather dull but it can be argued that the Grammar Translation method has over the years had a remarkable success. Millions of people have successfully learnt foreign languages to a high degree of proficiency and, in numerous cases, without any contact whatsoever with native speakers of the language (as was the case in the former Soviet Union, for example).

These square measure bound kinds of learner UN agency respond terribly absolutely to a grammatical information because it will provide them each a collection of clear objectives and a transparent sense of accomplishment. Different learners want the safety of the tongue and therefore the chance to relate grammatical structures to tongue equivalents. Above all, this sort of approach will provide learners a basic foundation upon that they will then build their communicative skills. On the one hand they need motivating communicative activities that facilitate to market their fluency and, on the opposite, they bit by bit acquire a sound and correct basis within the descriptive linguistics of the language. This combined approach is mirrored in several of the EFL course books presently being revealed and, amongst different things, suggests that the descriptive linguistics Translation methodology, off from being dead, is incredibly a lot of alive and kicking as we tend to enter the twenty first century. So while not a sound information of the grammatical basis of the language it may be argued that the learner is in possession of nothing quite a variety of communicative phrases that square measure dead adequate for basic communication.

Public institutions everywhere have been preaching the concept of grammar for years, yet for some mystical reason, society cannot seem to figure it out. If one is truly honest about the topic, he or she will have to admit that the collective grammar of this country is simply tragic. Into whose lap does this task fall? English teachers. Teaching English grammar to a group of students is a job that should grant super human status to any teacher who manages to do it successfully. There is a steaming buffet of options to pick from when it comes to choosing the best way to teach this age old and ever-relevant area of study. There is the new-age method of teaching grammar, which ironically doesn't actually teach grammar at all, but instead hopes students just sort of "pick it up" as they read different texts; then, there is a method somewhere in the middle, the "discuss some grammatical concept in a

mini-lesson format, then analyze that concept as students read and write" method. Each method depends on who is doing the teaching, what kind of students occupy the classroom, and the demands of the school system, and each method has plenty to smile about and sneer upon.

The traditional methodology of teaching synchronic linguistics continues to be highly regarded among full-fledged academics and academics that are within the profession for a minute. Everybody is aware of these styles of academics. They proclaim this world has gone to the deepest pits of hell within the roughest of hand baskets, and really the remainder of the academic's surprise why they're still teaching the least bit.

There are a few young, fresh, braves who enter the teaching field and follow the example set by their teachers in high school-- the traditional, grammar book, worksheet, right or wrong example. Regardless of whether they look at the student population and see the wasting away of society or a field of young and potential-filled flowers, these teachers see grammar as something that should be taught in isolation. It should be given its own time, its own unit, and its own space in the curriculum. Not incorrectly, they see their chosen field of study as something so highly important that it cannot be ignored nor tainted with other subjects; the students must learn it because, well, that's what students do: they learn grammar.

Well, there may be one fact these traditionalists are overlooking when it comes to teaching grammar. Why is it that students, when taught grammar the traditional, isolated way, have to be re-taught the same grammatical concepts year after year? It seems to the common observer that they're simply not learning it. They remember the concepts for the worksheet and the test but soon forget and have to learn the next year. Are teachers wasting their time trying to fill young minds with grammatical facts? If they're not, then why do so many adults who have graduated high school and gone through years of repetitive grammar instruction display horrific grammatical skills.

Based on this information, many have decided to abandon the practice of teaching grammar all-together. They have brushed it off as worthless and have instead chosen to cross their fingers in hopes that if students read enough and write enough, they will start to naturally see the

patterns of the English language. For some students this may work. In fact, it may work for many students. However, teachers may collide into a problem with this system. In every state, teachers have a curriculum to follow, a list of "to-do's" These curriculum lists usually contain a set of pure grammatical skills that the students must learn, and unless the teacher wants to rebel against the curriculum that teacher must teach those things, the endless dilemmas of the English teachers would arise. For those teachers who are neither traditional nor rebellious, there is a middle road of grammar instruction. This type of instruction combines grammar with reading and writing as an everyday experience in the classroom. This method is very much dependent on the teacher's creativity and his or her ability to weave grammar into every other area of the English classroom. It is by no means the easiest way to teach grammar, but as research has shown, it may be the most effective. It is definitely the method that takes the most time and creativity on the part of the teacher, but for a dedicated professional, these are both secondary concerns to the level of learning the students achieve. There are teachers who make the traditional method work; somehow they have found a way to get bits of information to implant themselves into student minds like tiny eggs of precious information. There are teachers who don't handle grammar at all, but they make their students read enough and write enough that somehow they pass their state tests and grow up with a basic knowledge of the concepts; and there are teachers who creatively combine grammar to other classroom activities.

Learning and teaching grammar requires some creativity in order to make learning grammar a communicative process (The way to learn is to do. Learn by doing. Doing is learning) So this would depend the grammar structure you are targeting, the learners' level, and what "learning grammar" means to the learner. Traditional method book exercises and worksheets are, also, helpful. A multi-faceted approach is practical. Grammar should be part of an integrated approach. Of course, there is any number of ways to consider an integrated approach. And, also, grammar items should not be taught in isolation. They can be, but in rigidly adhering to doing just one thing at a time. A target structure or target structures indicate direction and focus but other things may come up along the way and there's no sense, of course, in

ignoring them. Speaking is primary, and learning to use grammar should be integrated with speaking practice. Combine functions of language with grammar instruction. Still grammar requires some separate attention and focus apart from everything else in order to ensure a solid understanding. What is "modern" outside of an integrative approach which has a strong focus on grammar as a base and facilitating conversation in learning vocabulary, tenses, and sentence structure?

3. Conclusion

Most grammatical errors of non-native speakers of English would not be found among native speakers of English. Non-native speakers of English require explicit instruction in grammar forms, the meaning of those forms, and how and when to use the forms. Native speakers of English don't require this A point of instruction that may be common to both non-native speakers of English and native speakers of English would be utilizing the variety of grammatical form, combined with lexical choices, to produce better writing or to be a more articulate speaker. However, even for this purpose, the needs of native speakers and non-native speaker would not always be in alignment.

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